

Defect mitigation using multi-dentate ligand in FASnI₃ perovskite films

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Abstract

Tin-based perovskite shows a more rational band gap, along with lower exciton-binding energies, and is noted to be suitable for solar cell fabrication. One of the open questions is their lower environmental stability due to poor crystallinity and surface inhomogeneity. We probed the impact of sulfur-containing multi-functional additives in FASnI₃ thin films, which interact intensely with the Sn-based perovskites, and in turn, regulate the crystallization process to allow the preferential crystal growth along (h00) planes at the macroscale. The single sulfur-containing ammonium cation (Isothio-Br) based perovskites showed superior crystallinity and microstructure as compared to the double sulfur-containing Disulfo-Cl molecule.

Keywords: Perovskites, Lead-free; Additive; Isothio; Sn-based perovskites; Crystal growth

Introduction

Lead halide-based perovskites have shown ground-breaking advancements in boosting the solar cell's power conversion efficiency (PCE) from 3.8% to over 26% in just over a decade [1]. The synergetic effort from the scientific community also accelerated the laboratory scale to module fabrication. Despite such success, the potential toxicity of Lead (Pb) in both environmental and human health aspects imposed concern for industrial production from regulators. Arguably, the emergence of Pb-free halide perovskites has been identified as a potential alternative to address this challenge. Among the various available sources - such as Germanium (Ge), Bismuth (Bi), Antimony (Sb), Copper (Cu), and Tin (Sn), Sn-based perovskites have vouched as the suitable alternative due to their high carrier mobility, small exciton binding energy, ease of growth, and narrow band gap around 1.3 eV[1–4]. Although the Sn-perovskite was discovered and probed for solar cell application almost at the same time as Pb-perovskites back in 2012, various factors limited them from registering similar performance as their Pb-counterparts. The first solar cell fabricated with $\text{CsSnI}_{2.95}\text{F}_{0.05}$ doped with SnF_2 as hole conductor and dye N719 on a mesoporous TiO_2 measured 10.2% efficiency, which was higher than their Pb-counterpart at that time [5–7]. The Sn-perovskites then enjoy the privilege of being investigated from their first implantation as the p-type semiconductor for hole-transporting material in dye-sensitized solar cells to the light absorber layer in both single-junction and multi-junction perovskite solar cells [8].

Despite exceptional properties and accomplishment, FASnI_3 demonstrated much lower efficiencies (14.81%) compared to the Pb-perovskites (26%) [9]. Several limitations such as rapid oxidation of Sn^{2+} , poor film quality, and higher defect generation have been identified as responsible for this discrepancy. The higher activity of 5 s orbital electrons in Sn-perovskite than the 6 s orbital of Pb-perovskite leads to facile oxidation to Sn^{4+} .

The formation of the Sn^{4+} state results in a self-p-doping effect and deteriorates the photovoltaic performance of the fabricated solar cells [10–12]. Further, the poor film formation ability and rough morphology lead to small-size grains with defects. This obtained reduced crystallinity allows higher non-radiative recombination, which in turn limits, the open circuit voltage and fill factor of solar cells. Moreover, the reduced crystallinity impedes the light absorption and eventually decreases the short circuit current. The generated defects at the surface and the bulk of the thin films facilitate the encroachment of oxygen or moisture molecules, which further destabilizes the system [10,13–15].

Several strategies have been reported including the use of reducing agents, solvent engineering, surface passivation, and the use of molecular additives for improving the stability and performance of FASnI_3 -based solar cells [14]. The defect-passivation protocol, with molecular additives, has been preferred among the community. The electron-receiving nature of Lewis acids passivates the negative defects such as uncoordinated halide ions, whereas Lewis bases can neutralize the positively charged defects such as uncoordinated Sn ions via acting as a potential electron donor. Moreover, Lewis bases are known to manipulate the crystallization rates via intermediate formation [16–18]. Borrowing the findings from Lewis base additivisation in Pb-perovskites, multi-functional organic ammonium additives attracted huge attention [19–21]. Their role in directing the precursor solution chemistry, possible structural incorporation via ammonium cations, and antioxidant element presence to suppress the Sn^{2+} oxidation make them suitable potential ideal additives.

Owing to the low redox potential of Sn^{2+} it is more readily available to oxidation, and subsequently, yields low power conversion efficiency and stability. In this work, we adapted a Lewis-based additive engineering strategy to improve the crystallinity of the

FASnI₃ perovskite layer through a multi-dentate ligand. We have added two sulfur-containing ammonium salts to the precursor solution and their structural, optical, and elemental properties have been studied. With the optimized 5% additive engineering of Isothio-Br, we observed a significant enhancement in the surface crystallinity of the film.

Results and Discussions:

We employed two sulfur-containing organic ammonium salts, S-(2-Aminoethyl) isothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (Isothio-Br) and Cystamine dihydrochloride (Disulfo-Cl) as additives in the FASnI₃ precursor solution. The FASnI₃ precursor solution was spin-coated and annealed at 100 °C for 12 minutes. We recorded the UV-Vis absorption spectra from the annealed films (Figure 1A). Both the modified films showed a decrease in the absorption spectra with a blue-shifted bandgap, as depicted in the enlarged view. This bandgap shift may be attributed to the Bromine and Chlorine incorporation into the system. Since the operational stability has been the core issue for the FASnI₃ perovskite layer, we have performed a real-time absorbance tracking of the films for 3 minutes (measurement at every 10 s). We have conducted the experiment at room temperature (T= 25 C, RH=40-45%). It can be deduced from Figure 1B, that FASnI₃ showed considerable stability in the absorption in the low-energy region (800-900 nm) as highlighted in the inset, but the absorption coefficient dropped down in the high-energy region (400-600 nm). Disulfo-Cl films registered a drastic drop over the entire region (Figure 1C). Notably, as depicted in Figure 1D, the Isothio-Br films demonstrated slightly higher stability by maintaining a similar absorption coefficient in both high-energy and low-energy regions. This could be an indicator of the achieved stability enhancement.

Figure 1. (A) UV-Vis absorption spectra of thin films, Zoom-in view of 800-1000 nm region has been given in the inset. (B-D) real-time UV-Vis absorption tracking of thin films where each measurement was recorded at an interval of 10 s, inset image shows the zoom-in view of the low-energy region.

The stability of FASnI₃ film is directly related to their structural stability, thus, we probed the powder X-ray diffractograms of the deposited thin films (Figure 2A). All the films exhibited four peaks, indexing to the standard FASnI₃ peaks at $2\theta = 14^\circ$ (100), 24° (102), 28° (200) and 31° (122). However, unlike the Disulfo-Cl film, Isothio-Br films demonstrated much higher intensity for the (100) and (200) peaks indicating enhanced crystallinity. Furthermore, the peak area ratio shown in Figure 2B for (100) / (102) and (200) / (122) diffractions displays the preferred orientation of (h00) planes for Isothio-Br films. Enhanced peak intensity and the preferred (h00) orientation at the macroscopic

level indicate the crystallinity enhancement which could have originated from the suppressed defect density by Isothio-Br additive.

Figure 2. (A) Diffractograms collected for all three thin films, and green triangles indicate the reflections corresponding to the FTO substrate. (B) Peak area ratios are calculated from the diffractograms. (C, D) Zoom-in view (C) of (100) peak and (D) of low angle region.

Figure 2C depicts the zoom-in view of (100) diffraction and the red shift in the peak may be attributed to the iodide substitution by other halides in the additive molecules. The presence of ammonium cations may result in the formation of layered perovskites.

However, the zoom-in view of diffractograms at lower 2θ angles ($2\theta = 5\text{-}12^\circ$) in Figure 2D suggests the absence of any layered perovskite presence at the macroscopic level.

Figure 3. Proposed crystallization scheme for FASnI₃ and with Isothio-Br thin films. (A) Composition of precursor solution, (B) proposed interactions at intermediate phases, and (C) final crystal orientation of fabricated thin films.

From the above observations and available literature [19], we have proposed a working mechanism of Isothio-Br additive in this system depicted schematically (Figure 3). As shown in Figures 3A & B, the Isothio-Br has been added to the precursor solution and we anticipate strong interaction between the SnI₂ -- DMSO intermediate structure and Isothio-Br molecules. The ammonium ends, the bromine ion, and the electron-rich Sulfur element could trigger the interaction. Similar to the case of the FAPbI₃ layer [19], the Isothio-Br is speculated to be incorporated in the bulk as passivating the FA vacancy and at the surface due to their larger sizes. We speculate the possible passivation of iodide vacancy by the smaller Br element and the electron-rich sulfur component. We attribute the combined effects from ammonium ends and sulfur elements to the observed

preferential crystal growth at the macroscopic level. We performed the Kelvin probe microscopy experiments and the deduced work function from contact potential difference. The work function value was noted for FASnI_3 to be 4.77 eV, while the addition of additives led to the values of 4.87 eV with Disulfo-, and 4.88 eV for Isothio-, suggesting band bending on the additivization.

Figure 4. (A-F) SEM surface morphology of (A, B) FASnI_3 , (C, D) Disulfo-Cl, and (E, F) Isothio-Br thin films on different scale bars.

Further, we have examined the surface microstructure of the deposited thin films using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) as depicted in Figure 4. FASnI_3 film showed a

rough compact surface but the Disulfo-Cl film displayed poor surface coverage. This poor surface coverage is substantiated by the poor crystallinity and absorption behavior observed in Figures 1 and 2. On the other side, our Isothio-Br films improved the surface coverage with a compact smooth nature as in Figures 3E and F. The improvement in microstructure can be attributed to the improved crystallinity observed from the diffractogram.

Conclusion:

To summarize, we investigated the impact of sulfur-containing multi-functional additives in lead-free FASnI₃ thin films. This is noted to regulate the crystallization growth that occurs during the processing of solutions and thin-film deposition and improves the quality of the deposited thin film having uniform and compact crystalline grains. The Sn-based perovskite with a single sulfur-containing ammonium cation (Isothio-Br) gave improved crystallinity and surface microstructure when compared to the double sulfur-containing Disulfo-Cl molecule. The lower toxicity level and environmental acceptability with a judicious bandgap provide tin (Sn)-based perovskite solar cells as a promising alternative for solar cell application.

Experimental Details:

The perovskite precursor solution was prepared by dissolving an equimolecular amount of SnI₂ and FAI in DMSO solvent. We have added 10 mole % of SnF₂ in all the precursor solutions to suppress the Sn²⁺ oxidation. For additive engineering, we have added 5 mol % of commercially available additives in the precursor solution. The solution was stirred for 3 hours at 60 °C to ensure complete dissolution and brought to room temperature before the spin coating process.

The precursor solutions were further spin coated using a two-step process, 1000 rpm for 12s followed by 5000 rpm for 50 s, and the films were transferred to a hot plate at 100 °C and annealed for 12 minutes. The work function (Φ) and Fermi level of perovskites were determined with the help of a non-Scanning Kelvin Probe system (KP020) at a frequency of 0.1 – 10 Hz.

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